

Incorporating Social Value into Products of Social Enterprise for a New Brand Identity Case Study: Rumah Ismail

Fahmi Ilham Akbar¹, Melia Famiola²

¹ Master Student of Business Administration, School of Business and Management Bandung Institute of Technology, Bandung, Indonesia, 40132

² Professor Assistant, School of Business and Management Bandung Institute of Technology, Bandung, Indonesia, 40132

ABSTRACT: Rumah Ismail is a Community-Based Entrepreneurship Accelerator (CBEA) that accelerates community business generated from empowerment activities. The profits earned by Rumah Ismail are used for social activities such as charity programs and the provision of scholarships for school education for underprivileged children. This research aims to develop a sustainable communication model that effectively conveys Rumah Ismail's mission and social values to the stakeholders to enhance Rumah Ismail's brand. This research uses brand identity by Kapferer and Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) by Belch & Belch with the mixed methodology or combined approach between qualitative and quantitative methods. The results of this study indicate that Rumah Ismail needs to communicate its social values, namely increasing the added value of local products through empowering local talents as a new brand of Rumah Ismail by delivering a strong brand communication message through packaging so that the social values owned by Rumah Ismail can be conveyed effectively Suitable for all people stakeholders.

KEYWORDS: CBEA, Empowerment, Rumah Ismail, Social Enterprise, Social Mission, Social Value.

1. INTRODUCTION

Rumah Ismail is a business activity unit that was established in 2019 and is under a social foundation called the Generasi Ismail Mandiri Foundation. Rumah Ismail has a mission to become a center for creative entrepreneurship as well as a center for community empowerment so that it can have a positive impact on others. The initial goal of establishing Rumah Ismail was to run community empowerment programs. One was to help duck egg breeders who experienced losses in selling their livestock products when the Covid-19 pandemic started. Because many of their livestock products cannot be sold to the market, causing a decrease in their productivity level.

In 2022, Rumah Ismail carried out other empowerment activities. At that time, many housewives who lived under the poverty line could not work and had no income. Then Rumah Ismail also took the initiative to help empower them by providing skills training to make traditional food products, namely rengginang. The selection of this training is based on local capabilities, and several households already have rengginang businesses. Households with this capacity are then appointed as training facilitators funded by Rumah Ismail.

Rumah Ismail acts as a Community-Based Entrepreneurship Accelerator (CBEA) or a community-based business accelerator in this empowerment activity. Community-based enterprises (CBEs) focus on the symbiotic relationship that different people and organizations are mutually dependent on and the creation of social value for the community in the long term (Pinheiro et al., 2020).. Therefore, the terms used to represent community-based entrepreneurship are multidimensional and diverse in approaches which may be viewed as routes and directions for promoting entrepreneurship in the communities (Hasan et al., 2021). In this role, Rumah Ismail serves as an accelerator for the business activities of empowered assisted communities and makes them strategic partners. The empowered community members are given skills training to produce their products. They are given loans as interest-free start-up capital for those without capital to carry out their initial business activities. Then the products can be sold directly through Rumah Ismail or to other people. The role of Rumah Ismail as CBEA here will bring and accelerate their products to enter the market so that their products can have a need that matches their target market.

The business problem that Rumah Ismail is currently facing is that there are still customers who view products from Rumah Ismail as just ordinary products, not as products of empowerment that have a social mission for the community. It surely becomes a challenge for Rumah Ismail to find out how to convey the values of the fostered products from the empowerment activities carried

out by Rumah Ismail as well as ways to communicate these values and the social mission of Rumah Ismail effectively to customers to market their products.

This research aims to develop a sustainable communication model by creating clear and consistent messages, highlighting the impact of product purchases, tailoring messages to target customers, and using the most effective communication channels to reach them. So that the values of the products developed by Rumah Ismail can reach customers who can become a competitive advantage from products marketed by Rumah Ismail for potential customers, and customers see that Rumah Ismail's products have higher values than buying ordinary products. Thus, Rumah Ismail can increase sales of Rumah Ismail products and increase its social impact on society.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Social Enterprise Teasdale (2012) highlighted that “social enterprise” is a fluid and contested concept affected by three variables: (1) it is constructed by diverse actors promoting different discourses, (2) it is connected to different organizational forms, and (3) it is based on different academic theories. Social enterprises emerge as an economical alternative, having self-sufficiency as a basic principle (Csoba, 2020).

Alter (2007) mentions that Social enterprises can be classified based on their mission orientation : a. Mission-Centric Social Enterprise

The enterprise is central to the organization's social mission. These social enterprises are created for the express purpose of advancing the mission using a self-financing model. b. Mission-Related Social Enterprise

The enterprise is related to the organization's mission or core social services. Mission-related social enterprises have synergistic properties, creating social value for programs and generating economic value to subsidize the organization's social programs and/or operating expenses.

c. Social Enterprise Unrelated to Mission

The enterprise is not related to the organization's mission, or intended to advance the mission other than by generating income for its social programs and operating costs. Business activities may have a social bent, add marketing or branding value, operate in an industry related to the nonprofit parent organization's services or sector, however, profit potential is the motivation for creating a social enterprise unrelated to mission.

2..2 Brand Identity

Kapferer (2012) proposed the new brand identity in a brand identity prism model. Kapferer explained that in a brand identity there are six dimensions which are described as follows:

Figure 2.1 Brand Identity Prism Model (source: Kapferer, 2012)

In the prism of brand identity, Kapferer (2012) identifies six aspects of brand identity that can be seen from two sides, namely the source (brand) and the recipient (consumer). An explanation of brand identity is explained as follows:

- a. Capabilities: the tangible and intangible resources a brand possesses to help it deliver its products or services.
- b. Internal culture & values: the culture and values embedded within the organization that helps shape the brand's identity.
- c. Noble purpose: a higher mission or goal a brand strives to achieve beyond profit.
- d. Personality: the unique characteristics that differentiate a brand from its competitors.
- e. Shared values & community: the values that the brand and its customers share and the community that forms around the brand.
- f. Aspirational self-image: the image the brand wants to project to its customers and the market.
- g. Rallying Cry: a tagline or slogan encapsulating the brand's message and purpose.

2.3 Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC)

According to Belch & Belch (2018), Integrated marketing communications or known as Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC), is a concept of marketing communications planning that introduces the added value of a comprehensive plan that evaluates the strategic role of various communication disciplines for example, general advertising, direct response, sales promotion, and PR and combines these disciplines to provide clarity, consistency and maximum communication impact.

Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) is one of the many processes available to build customer relationships. What sets Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) apart from other customer-centric processes is that communication is at the heart of all relationships and is also a circular process (Belch & Belch : 2018).

Figure 2.2 Promotional Mix as a Tools for IMC (Source: Belch & Belch, 2018)

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This research uses a mixed or combined approach between qualitative and quantitative methods. According to Creswell (2007), research using mixed methods is a research approach that combines qualitative and quantitative research. There are three strategies in mixed methods, namely: (1) Sequential mixed methods strategy, including (a) sequential explanatory strategy, (b) sequential exploratory strategy, and (c) sequential transformative strategy (2) concurrent mixed methods strategy, including (a) Concurrent triangulation strategy, (b) Concurrent embedded strategy, and (c) Concurrent transformative strategy (3) Transformative mixed methods strategy.

3.2 Data Collection

The sources of data in this research are divided into two types, which are:

- a. Primary Data, The primary data collection uses surveys analysis through questionnaires via google form to the target market. The survey will question the audience's perceptioofut Rumah Ismail' proposed model of IMC and a brand as a social enterprise. In addition, data will be collected through focus group discussion activities with the founders of Rumah Ismail to dig deeper and to equate perceptions of the social mission of Rumah Ismail.
- b. Secondary Data, The secondary is using desk research, where the data will be collected through books, journals, institutional reports, internal data from the company, and also from reliable resources on the internet such as websites, social media, and other channels available that correlate.

3.3 Population and sample

The sample for this study is made up using The following Slovin's equation, with a 10% error tolerance, is used to get this number.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

n = Number of Samples N = Population Size e = Margin of Error

The number of samples are obtained from 218 Rumah Ismail's customer that occurred during 2021.

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \frac{218}{1 + 218 (10\%)^2} \\ &= 99,2537 \end{aligned}$$

The total sample for this research is 99,2537. The writer decided to complete the 100 sample respondents for the questionnaire. The questionnaire is then distributed using simple random sampling, a sampling technique that randomly takes samples from Rumah Ismail's customers.

3.4 Data Analysis

The data analysis technique used in this research is data analysis using descriptive analysis. Descriptive analysis, according to Sugiyono (2014: 21), is a descriptive analysis method is a statistic used to analyze data by describing or describing the data that has been collected as it is without intending to make general conclusions or generalizations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Internal Analysis Brand Identity of Rumah Ismail by Kapferer

In conducting an internal analysis of the brand identity of Rumah Ismail, the research was carried out using focus group discussions (FGD). The FGD results contain opinions about the questions asked to the founders of Rumah Ismail to understand what missions and values are owned by Rumah Ismail. In addition, through the FGD method, researchers also want to dig deeper into the missions and values that Rumah Ismail holds today. In the future, as for each question in this FGD activity based on the latest theory about brand identity by Kapferer, The following is a presentation of the FGD activities' results with the four founders of Rumah Ismail.

Figure 4.1 Brand Identity Model of Rumah Ismail After Holding FGD with the Founder (Source: Author, 2023)

4.2 Eksternal Analysis Brand Identity by Kapferer

For external analysis, researchers used a survey method by distributing questionnaires to 100 respondents where respondents were customers of Rumah Ismail products who had purchased Rumah Ismail products. The question points of the questionnaire are based on the elements of the brand Identity theory by Kapferer. This survey was conducted to understand the perceptions of customers and potential customers about the brand identity of Rumah Ismail.

Table 4.1 Demography of Survey Respondents (Source: Author, 2022)

No	Demography of Costumers	Description
1.	Age	20-45
2.	Domicile	Sukabumi, Bandung, Jakarta, Bogor
3.	Education	High school to Doctoral
4.	Profession	Private employees, government employees, freelancers, businessmen/women, students

The conclusion of the results of the survey regarding Rumah Ismail's customers' perceptions of the company is as follows:

- a. The majority of the respondents (45%) strongly agree and 38% agree that Rumah Ismail's products have good quality, with only 17% having a neutral response.
- b. Regarding Rumah Ismail's internal culture and values, a similar number of respondents agreed (36%) and strongly agreed (36%) that the company has social values embodied in it. However, there were still 28% who had a neutral response. Similarly, 46% agreed that Rumah Ismail has a family culture in running its business activities, with 28% agreed and 26% neutral.
- c. 50% of the respondents strongly agreed and 35% agreed that Rumah Ismail has a positive impact on the environment, while 47% strongly agreed and 32% agreed that the company has a social mission to have a greater impact on others.
- d. 47% of the respondents agreed that Rumah Ismail has a personality and social image, 29% were neutral, and 22% strongly agreed. However, 2% disagreed, indicating an opportunity for the company to strengthen its brand image as a product of the community and social empowerment.
- e. 55% of the respondents agreed, and 33% strongly agreed that they feel they are helping others by purchasing Rumah Ismail's products.
- f. 37% of the respondents strongly agreed, and 33% agreed that they feel they are useful people by buying Rumah Ismail's products, with 30% being neutral.
- g. 60% of the respondents agreed, and 31% strongly agreed that the slogan "one action for three good things" conveys Rumah Ismail's strong social mission message.

Overall, the results suggest that Rumah Ismail's customers have a positive perception of the company's products and its impact on the environment and others, as well as its social mission. However, there is still room for improvement in terms of customers perceiving the company's internal culture and values, as well as its personality and social image.

4.3 Integrated Marketing Communication

So far, the marketing strategy carried out by Rumah Ismail has mostly been carried out through online channels, especially on WhatsApp status. Where the strategy via WhatsApp is the most powerful strategy among the others. because in addition to strengthening awareness, it can also strengthen engagement with existing customers. Moreover, Rumah Ismail has not used other channels in marketing its products so far. Because the founders feel that marketing products and informing customers about social activities carried out is far more effective via WhatsApp and word of mouth than marketing through other channels.

Table 4.2 Existing Marketing Strategy of Rumah Ismail (Source: Author,2023)

No	Channel	Content
Offline		
1.	Word of Mouth	Recommendation from one customer to another
2.	Exhibition	Promoting products directly to customers through activities in various exhibitions
Online		
3.	Whatsapp	Contains content from Rumah Ismail products via WhatsApp status or directly promoting via direct message to the costumers
4.	Instagram	featuring various products from Rumah Ismail
5.	Website	Showing the social activities of Rumah Ismail

The result of the survey analysis on the respondents' perceptions of the suggested Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) model for Rumah Ismail, which consisted of marketing through social media and advertising, is as follows:

- a. Respondents showed a positive reception of the advertising done by Rumah Ismail, with 59% of respondents agreeing and 34% strongly agreeing.

- b. The majority of customers (59%) agreed to the use of sales promotion where 50% of the profits are used for social activities such as charity and tuition assistance for dropouts.
- c. The preferred platform for customers to receive information about products with a social mission was social media, with 72% of respondents choosing this option and Instagram being the most preferred platform (62%).
- d. Photos of social activities were found to be the most effective media in encouraging customer interest in buying products with a social mission (44%), followed by campaigns (27%) and product photos (18%).
- e. If Rumah Ismail shares photos or videos of its social activities on social media, the customer's interest is expected to increase, as 60% of respondents strongly agreed and 39% agreed to this statement. Respondents expressed an interest in increasing their interaction with Rumah Ismail via social media (52% agreed, 40% strongly agreed).
- f. Uploading testimonials about Rumah Ismail's products and social mission also increased customer interest, with 65% of respondents fully agreeing with this statement.
- g. Rumah Ismail product packaging was found unclear in conveying information about its mission and social activities, with 30% of respondents reporting neutrality. However, consumers said they would be more interested if a strong message was conveyed through product packaging, with 59% of respondents fully agreeing with this statement.

Based on these insights, Rumah Ismail's proposed IMC model includes advertising, merchandising, digital/internet marketing, and packaging. The advertising strategy should focus on communicating the brand's identity, values, mission, and social activism to customers via its preferred platform, Instagram. The promotional strategy should emphasize the social aspect of the brand, with a focus on philanthropy and community impact. Packaging should also be designed to clearly communicate the brand's mission and social activities to attract customers further and increase their interest in the brand. Overall, the focus of the IMC model is to build brand awareness, communicate brand values and social mission, and effectively use social media and other marketing channels to retain customers.

5. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this research is to find out how the brand identity of Rumah Ismail as a social enterprise that has a social mission in empowering the community and the IMC strategy used to convey its social mission to the specified target customer, namely customers who buy products by not only oriented to meet their basic needs but customers who are already at the level of transcendence or in other words customers who are oriented to the impact of the products. Based on the research results, brand identity and IMC strategies positively and significantly impact consumer perceptions of a company's products which can increase customer buying interest. One of the strategies that can be done is strengthening the message conveyed in the product packaging. Rumah Ismail can visually describe the mission, and social activities carried out in the packaging. So that the message conveyed can be conveyed well and customer interest can increase even higher as well as the empowerment activities carried out by Rumah Ismail can have a more significant impact on the community.

REFERENCES

1. Alter, K. (2007). Social enterprise typology. *Virtue Ventures LLC*, 12(1), 1-124.
2. Arikunto, S. (2010). *Metode penelitian*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta, 173.
3. Austin, J., Stevenson, H., & Wei-Skillern, J., (2006), Social and commercial entrepreneurship: Same, different, or both?, *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 30(1), 1—22.
4. Ayozie, D. O., Ndubueze, A. K., & Uche, A. V. (2011). Ethical issues involved in integrated marketing communication in Nigeria. *Business Management Dynamics*, 1(4), 50.
5. Belch and Belch (2018). *Advertising and promotion an Integrated Marketing Communication Perspective*. New York. McGraw-Hill.
6. Bungin, B. (2007). *Metodologi penelitian kualitatif: Aktualisasi metodologis ke arah ragam varian kontemporer*. Jakarta. Grasindo.
6. Creswell, J. W., & Tashakkori, A. (2007). Differing perspectives on mixed methods research. *Journal of mixed methods research*, 1(4), 303-308.
7. Csoba, J., & Csoba, J. (2020). *The Characteristics of Social Cooperatives in Hungary*.

8. Revitalisation of the Household Economy: Social Integration Strategies in Disadvantaged Rural Areas of Hungary, 159-173.
9. Dodson, S. E., Kukic, I., Scholl, L., Pelfrey, C. M., & Trochim, W. M. (2021). A protocol for retrospective translational science case studies of health interventions. *Journal of Clinical and Translational Science*, 5(1), e22.
10. Gulo, W. 2002. *Research Method*. Jakarta: Grasindo.
11. Hadi, S. (2002). *Metodologi Riset*, Yogyakarta. Andi Offset.
12. Hassan, F. A. T. I. M. A. H., Dahalan, N. O. R. Z. I. A. N. I., Hilmi, M. F., & Jaafar, M. A.
13. S. T. U. R. A. (2021). Understanding the concept of community-based entrepreneurship: a systematic review approach. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government*, 27(02).
14. Holt, D., & Littlewood, D. (2015). Identifying, mapping, and monitoring the impact of hybrid firms. *California Management Review*, 57(3), 107-125.
15. Jobber, D., & Lancaster, G. (2009). *Selling and Sales management*. 8. p. Harlow. Pearson Education. Viitattu, 9, 2017.
16. Kapferer, JN, 2012, *The New Strategic Brand Management, Advanced Insights & Strategic Thinking*, Kogan Page Ltd., London. p. 149-177.
17. Kliatchko, J.G. 2008, Revisiting the IMC construct, *International Journal of Advertising*, Vol. 27 No. 1, pp. 133-160.
18. Koetjaraningrat, (1981). *Kebudayaan Mentalitas dan Pembangunan*. Jakarta: Gramedia.
19. Leagnavar, P., Leone, F., & Nagasaki, T. (2016). Measuring impact: How business accelerates the sustainable development goals.
20. Marshall, C. & Gretchen, B. R. (2008). *Designing qualitative research*. Sage Publications.
21. Percy, L. (2008). *Strategic integrated marketing communication: theory and practice*. Published by Elsevier Inc.
22. Pinheiro, S., Granados, M. L., and Assunção, M. (2020) 'Local incentive structures and the constitution of community-based enterprises in the forest', *World Development Perspectives*, Vol 20, pp. 100243.
23. Roberts, L., & Henderson, J. (2009). Paramedics' perceptions of their role, education, training and working relationships when attending cases of mental illness. *Australasian Journal of Paramedicine*, 7(3).
24. Sagoe, D. (2012). Precincts and prospects in the use of focus groups. *Social and Behavioural Science Research*, 17 (29), 1 – 16.
25. Sarjono, Haryadi dan Julianita, Winda. (2011). *SPSS VS Lisrel Sebuah Pengantar Aplikasi Untuk Riset*. Penerbit Salemba Empat. Jakarta-Indonesia.

Cite this Article: Fahmi Ilham Akbar, Melia Famiola (2023). Incorporating Social Value into Products of Social Enterprise for a New Brand Identity Case Study: Rumah Ismail. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 6(4), 2319-2326